

MENTAL ARITHMETIC: THE ART OF SKILL

Abduxamidov Sardor

Academy Of Sciences Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan M.T. Doctoral
School Of The Orozboyev Institute Of Seismic Resistance Of Mechanics
And Constructions

Abduxamidova Nafosat

Student Of Samarkand State University
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ABSTRACT

This article discusses mental arithmetic, the benefits and origins of mental arithmetic. Some examples and problems related to mental arithmetic are explored.

It is known that only 5% of people can prove themselves in various fields and reach the heights they want in life. The other 95 percent of people only set goals, but never reach them. Because of this, the left hemisphere of the brain of these people develops faster than the right hemisphere. These people, who are considered to have no equal in terms of logical thinking, do not use the inner feelings and imagination that nature has given them. Mental arithmetic allows both hemispheres of the brain to develop equally. The history of mental arithmetic comes from Eastern culture. Mental arithmetic is an important civilizational achievement in ancient China. Using Mental Arithmetic imagery, students can see, hear, touch, and brain to coordinate body functions while counting, promote balanced development of left and right brains, and create imagination in the brain to achieve the best development of the whole brain. will give. Mental Arithmetic program focuses on concentration, logic, imagination, analytical thinking, creative thinking. Children studying in this program can achieve success not only in mathematics, but also in other fields of science. Here they will have self-confidence and ability to overcome difficulties[1-2].

Mental arithmetic helps parents when it is difficult for children to be interested in reading due to the fact that there are many distractions nowadays. Mental arithmetic allows both hemispheres of the brain to develop equally. The goal of this science, which appeared in Japan 2000 years ago, is to activate the entire mental potential with the help of calculation arithmetic.

Mental arithmetic helps to develop both hemispheres by using fine motor skills and precise arithmetic movements. As a result of the training, the child's activity and initiative will grow. The child stops getting tired, learns school lessons easily, participates in creative and technical circles with interest, learns foreign languages quickly. In addition, independence, self-confidence and leadership qualities are formed in the child.[1-2]

Children who start doing mental arithmetic do more finger exercises, which has many benefits. The child has been exercising his fingertips since he was young. How do you say? A child's crawling, holding things, and playing with toys are also initial exercises for a child. When a child crawls, his fingers are actively moving, and through this, fine motor skills are well developed, the development of speech is inextricably linked with fine motor skills, doctors say that the ability to control the fingertips and their own movements is the brain's response to speech. directly related to parts. In recent years, attention has been paid to the movements of the limbs, especially the movements of the fingers. Exercising the tips of the fingers stimulates the work of brain cells, so there are many smart children who learn to play the violin or piano early. Mental arithmetic is one of these exercises, because mental arithmetic mainly works with the fingertips, which helps the brain to work well and increase mental activity.[1-2]

The part of our brain that controls the muscles of the hands and face is much larger than the other parts that respond to body movements. Here it becomes clear how brain development is related to fine motor skills. Mental arithmetic is more suitable for children between the ages of 4 and 16. At this time, the child's brain is relatively flexible and tends to process a large amount of information. The main thing is to facilitate the process of learning mental arithmetic. In addition to the abacus, special platforms for gadgets are also used during training. They are designed to repeat the previous topic and do homework.

In conclusion, it can be said that I think that mental arithmetic will greatly help the development of the youth of Uzbekistan. The reason why Chinese children work with two hemispheres and they are engaged in several jobs at the same time is that they have well-developed mental arithmetic. As a result of children engaged in mental arithmetic, working with two hands, counting, drawing, both hemispheres of children work, and as a result, these children create good opportunities for creativity, study and action possible Especially, it is very useful for children who learn freely. Then it causes an increase in confidence, knowledge, and interest in life. Let's create opportunities for our young generation to make inventions, create innovations, and run freely like Chinese children. This mental arithmetic greatly helps our children to be able to count quickly, learn logic quickly, and develop leadership skills. [1]

Currently, the prices of studying in mental arithmetic courses are expensive, not everyone can afford to study and teach in these courses, so in the coming years, mental development like China will not be observed in Uzbekistan. The solution to this is to include mental arithmetic as a subject in HEIs and to teach students another innovative science - mental arithmetic[2].

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